

REMORA

Small fishes in a big pond

D5.1

COMMUNICATION & DISSEMINATION PLAN

Madeira Regional Directorate of Environment and Sea

Funded by
the European Union

REMORA 2024 - 2027

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SUMMARY

The REMORA project's Communication-Dissemination-Exploitation (CDE) plan focuses on maximizing the visibility, accessibility, and impact of its results, with specific strategies tailored to engage stakeholders and ensure the feasibility and sustainability of its outcomes. It was prepared to serve as a guiding document for REMORA's communication team, steering committee and advisory board members. The document first describes the methodology used for the elaboration of the plan, REMORA's objectives in terms of communication, dissemination, exploitation, the CDE framework (ie targeted stakeholders, main information, communication tools and channels). It then presents the strategy for each group of stakeholders. Finally it proposes to explore complementary exploitation pathways.

- ✓ **Objective:** to serve as a Reference document (all information in one place) and guide (how to communicate, disseminate, exploit according to each stakeholder)
- ✓ **Audience:** the CDE was prepared for REMORA consortium and Advisory board members.

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

AB: Advisory Board
CDE: Communication, Dissemination, Exploitation
CSA: Coordination and support action
DMP: Data Management Plan
EC: European Commission
ERA: European Research Area
ERDF: European Regional Development Fund
ESIF: European Structural & Investments Funds
EU : European Union
FP: Framework Programme
HRS4R: Human resources strategy for researchers
IP: Intellectual property
KPI: Key Performance Indicators
NCP: National Contact Point
OR: Outermost Regions
R&I: Research & Innovation
RI: Research Infrastructures
RRI: Responsible Research & Innovation
WP : Work Packages

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INTRODUCTION

1. Presentation of REMORA

The growing innovation divide across the European Union appears particularly detrimental to small and emerging regional research and innovation systems like the Outermost Regions¹ (OR). With limited resources, these regions struggle to reach the critical mass needed to build comparative advantages and become knowledge societies. Though the European Research Area (ERA) and the Framework Programme (FP) could compensate this marginalization through greater knowledge circulation, resources sharing and talents mobilities, the Outermost Regions present a limited participation in FP7 and Horizon 2020. This underutilization notably stems from the competing relations between European Structural & Investments Funds (ESIF) and the framework programs or “substitution effect”: many organizations and individuals prioritize easily accessible ESIF, decide not to apply to the FP and end up in “substitution trap” which isolates them from promising collaborations.

To move Outermost Regions’ R&I organizations and systems from substitution to synergies, REMORA ambitions to transform three Ocean and Marine ESIF-funded institutions in La Réunion, Madeira and the Azores into Horizon Europe champions: **CITEB** – the Technical Center for Blue Economy of La Reunion, **OKEANOS** – the Institute of Marine Sciences of the University of the Açores and **OOM** - the Oceanic Observatory of Madeira. To that end, REMORA will enhance their competitiveness (notably human resources, knowledge transfer and innovation capacities), strategic positioning and connections with major EU networks through a joint internationalization strategy with the support of **ARDITI** – the Regional Agency for the Development of Research, Technology and Innovation of Madeira, **RUIZIA** – a research SME from La Reunion specializing in Peripheries regional development, the Marine Institute of **Denmark Technical University** and **ERINN**, a Marine Impact & Innovation expert SME.

REMORA will then use the successful transformation of these 3 role models to lead other ESIF-oriented R&I organizations and policy-makers in Outermost and Widening Regions on the path to synergies.

2. Presentation of the Deliverable 5.1 “Communication, Dissemination, Exploitation plan”

REMORA’s Work Package n°5 aims at maximizing spillovers of the project at regional, national and EU level, through communication / dissemination activities beyond the consortium. Specifically, WP5 is designed to (i) ensure the visibility of REMORA and raise awareness on project activities; (ii) facilitate the replicability of REMORA’s approach to foster synergies in other regions, notably the 6 remaining Outermost Regions and other Widening territories. To reach WP5 objectives, three tasks were defined: (**Task 5.1**) Actualization of the Communication/Dissemination/Exploitation (CDE) plan; (**Task 5.2**) REMORA branding material and joint internationalization strategy promotion kit; (**Task 5.3**) – Dissemination of project results to other Widening regions and organizations.

During the proposal preparation, the consortium developed a preliminary plan that has been refined and updated in the initial months of project implementation. This updated document constitutes the **Deliverable D5.1 "Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation (CDE) Plan."** It reflects evolving strategies and activities to ensure effective communication, broad dissemination of project

¹ The European Union (EU) counts nine outermost regions, which are integral part of the Union and geographically distant from the continent: Azores, Canaries, Guadeloupe, Guyana, Madeira, Mayotte, Martinique, Réunion and Saint Martin.

results, and optimal exploitation of outcomes, aligning with the project's objectives and partner contributions.

Tailored to engage target groups effectively, the plan is built upon four key aspects: (i) the purpose of outreach to specific groups (Why), (ii) the relevant messages to convey (What), (iii) the appropriate channels and activities for delivery (How), and (iv) the timing of these actions (When).

Additionally, it includes an Intellectual Property (IP) strategy that ensures proper protection and exploitation measures. These are aligned with the consortium agreement, which defines ownership and pathways for the exploitation of results, including joint outputs. Developed for M6, the plan will be reviewed and updated as necessary to remain relevant throughout the project lifecycle.

I. METHODOLOGY TO UPDATE REMORA’s CDE PLAN

Based on the preliminary draft developed at proposal phase, REMORA CDE plan was updated through a multi-step process as described in the following section.

1. Establishing a Communication Team:

A dedicated team was formed to coordinate efforts and oversee the update process. The team is composed 7 members :

- the Impacts/Dissemination manager, in charge of the update process
- the Project coordinator
- and 5 correspondents from the partners designated as « Communication referees » by their organization

On the 7 members, 5 are CDE practitioners.

2. Drawing Inspiration from EC recommendations and Exemplary CDE Practices:

The latest EC recommendations about CDE good practices were used, notably materials from:

- The Webinar session: Dissemination & Exploitation in Horizon Europe (9 June 2021) <https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/docs/h2020-funding-guide/other/event210609.htm>
- The « Coordinators Day Synergies » (6 June 2024)

Also, notable examples of communication and dissemination were analyzed to guide improvements, notably CDE plans from the projects presented in table 1.

Table 1. Horizon project’s CDE plans used by REMORA for inspiration

Acronym	Title	Type	Coord.
EmpowerUs	Socio-Economic empowerment of Coastal communities	Community engagement	NORLANDSFORSKNING AS
PREP4BLUE	Preparing the research and innovation core for Mission Ocean, Seas and Waters	Mission Science-Policy dialogue	IFREMER
BOLSTER	Bridging Organizations and marginalized communities for Local Sustainability Transitions in Europe	Community engagement	TILBURG UNIVERSITY
Synergies	Innovating Preparedness by Leveraging SYNERGIES and Enhancing Results of DRM Projects	Citizens / multiactors dialogue	Deep Blue
GEECCO	Gender Equality in Engineering through Communication and Commitment	Gender integration in CDE	TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITAET WIEN
Pureef-y	Past, present and future status and mitigation for Cyprus shallow-water reef biodiversity		CMMI CYPRUS MARINE AND MARITIME INSTITUTE

This benchmark shows:

- similarities in goals / wording but also interesting ideas for REMORA:

- in terms of Communication: all projects aim to raise awareness, inform, educate, and engage stakeholders ; some present specificities, linked to the project general objectives (« community-driven engagement » ; « policy dialogue » ; « citizens engagement » ; « gender sensitive communication »)
 - in terms of Dissemination: all of them aim to share knowledge, promote best practices, and tailor dissemination to different audiences – but also inspiring channels/activities (community events and public forums, science cafés, industry reports and technological showcases)
 - in terms of Exploitation: all projects aim to facilitate uptake, generate impact, and ensure sustainability but some provide very interesting original pathways (« community-driven strategies for long-term sustainability » ; « policy integration » ; « Knowledge transfer methodologies » ; « practical guidelines and toolkits for futher exploitation »).
- alternative layouts which can be summarized into 2 types of structure as presented in table 2.

Table 2 Potential formats for REMORA CDE Plan

Type 1 : Global approach	Type 2 : Stakeholder perspective
1. Introduction/Background	1. Introduction/Background
2. Objectives	2. Objectives
3. Stakeholder Analysis	3. Stakeholder group 1
4. Key Messages	a. Key Messages
5. Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation Activities	b. Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation Activities
6. Timeline and Milestones ; Roles and Responsibilities	4. Stakeholder group 2
7. Monitoring and Evaluation	a. Key Messages
	b. Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation Activities
	5. Timeline and Milestones ; Roles and Responsibilities
	6. Monitoring and Evaluation

3. Identifying Partner Practices:

To ensure our REMORA plan aligns with the practices and capacities of partners, we initiated a collaborative approach using a structured questionnaire to which CITEB, OOM, OKEANOS and ERINN answered in August 2024 This tool gathered detailed insights into partners' usual communication channels, resources, target audiences, and prior experiences in CDE activities. By integrating their established methods, we aim to create a plan that builds on existing strengths and on specific needs. This participatory approach ensures the plan's practicality, relevance, and shared commitment to its successful implementation.

The main results of this questionnaire are presented in table 3 & 4. The detailed results of are available [online](#) in REMORA's folder.

Table 3. Summary of REMORA partners' CDE competencies and needs

	Strengths	Weaknesses	Challenges / Needs as identified by partners:
Communication	Targets easy to reach: - Outermost citizens, - Educational institutions, - Policymakers	Targets challenging to reach: - Outermost R&I organizations - General public - Local businesses	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - specialized HR in communication matters and data processing - No dedicated staff (researchers are in charge of the communication on their respective research fields/organization's activities or news), limited specific budget - Reaching the right audience, communication range of services effectively - Lack of specialized technicians and equipment due to budget constraints - Need for Training on social media practices
	Common channels: - Website, Social Media, newsletters	Channels that are less used by partners: - Direct emails	
	Common activities: - Events / webinars - Publications/reports	Activities less mastered : - Media campaigns (including social media)	
Dissemination	Targets easy to reach: - Scientific communities & policy-makers at local, regional, national and EU levels	Targets challenging to reach : - Industries	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Lack of specialized technicians and equipment due to budget constraints - Need for Training on social media practices
	Common dissemination methods : - Articles, - Scientific platform (ResearchGate...) - Public repository - Blogs, social media - Workshops - Exhibitions	Methods that are less used by partners : - Policy briefs	
Exploitation	Strategies commonly used - Knowledge transfer / training services - Contract research services	Strategies challenging for partners - IPR - Commercialization/partnership with industry - Consultancy services	<p>Few activities put in place to actually exploit research /project results.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Only 2 partners train their staff on Exploitation - Only 1 partner has a systematic approach for KT

4. Engaging Communication team through Workshops:

Collaborative workshops were held with partners to refine objectives, craft messages, identify suitable channels, and define planned activities.

The first workshop, held on October 30th, convened the communication team to advance the CDE plan update. The session opened with an engaging project overview, designed to help team members understand its intricate and distinctive aspects, thereby strengthening their ability to communicate effectively about it. This was followed by a presentation of the European Commission's definitions of Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation to establish a shared understanding of each

dimension’s objectives. The workshop concluded with collaborative discussions focusing on key elements of the preliminary plan, including general information, expected results, expected outcomes & impacts, and target audiences.

A second workshop was held on November 12th to work with the communication team to refine the plans’ objectives, key messages, priority channels, key activities, ensuring alignment with the project's vision and partner expectations.

Presentation supports for Workshops are available here:

- [Workshop 1](#)
- [Workshop 2](#)

5. Drafting the Updated Plan

Based on inputs and discussions, this update plan was developed to align with shared goals and priorities. The draft will be shared with the communication team and coordination team for comments/feedbacks, and then revised by the Steering committee members before submission by EC.

II. REMORA CDE's OBJECTIVES AND FRAMEWORK

The CDE plan is designed to maximize the project's impacts and ensure its sustainability beyond the EU funding period. To achieve this, the plan identifies and organizes key elements essential to effective implementation:

- Key principles and rules
- Targeted Stakeholders
- Project Description
- Main Communication & Dissemination tools and channels

1. Key principles and rules

a. Definitions

REMORA CDE Plan was elaborated in line with the European Commission (EC) definitions which distinguishes communication, dissemination, exploitation.

Figure 1. Introduction to the concepts of Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation (Source : EC)

b. Funding visibility

Communication activities of the partners related to REMORA (including media relations, conferences, seminars, information material, such as brochures, leaflets, posters, presentations, etc., in electronic form, via traditional or social media, etc.), dissemination activities and any infrastructure, equipment, vehicles, supplies or major result funded by the grant must acknowledge EU support and display the European flag (emblem) and funding statement (translated into local languages, where appropriate):

Example of mention :

Funded by the
European Union

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement no. 101159246.

c. Communication/Dissemination/Exploitation rules and IP Rights strategy

As outlined in REMORA's grant agreement with the European Commission, each partner is obligated to disseminate their results as soon as feasible in a publicly accessible format, subject to restrictions due to intellectual property protection, security rules, or legitimate interests. To support Open Science principles, partners must ensure open access to peer-reviewed scientific publications relating to their results. Additionally, partners are required to use their best efforts — up to four years after the project's conclusion — to exploit their results, either directly or through transfer or licensing to other entities.

Each partner is responsible for protecting their own results. For jointly generated results, the owners must agree on all protection measures and the division of related costs in advance. The protection of results must be adequate in duration and territorial scope, justified by considerations such as commercial potential, the legitimate interests of other partners, and any other relevant factors. According to the consortium agreement, results are owned by the party that generates them, while joint ownership is shared among contributors based on the inventors' respective contributions.

To address these obligations, REMORA will implement IP rights strategy to ensure compliance and effective management. Central to this strategy is the early identification and classification of all intellectual property generated, including data, tools, and methodologies. An IPR plan will be developed, detailing procedures for protection, use, and access to project results. This plan incorporates patenting or other legal protections for commercially valuable outputs.

To safeguard results before dissemination, exploitation, or communication, an IP assessment form has been created. This form, available in the consortium's shared folder, ensures that results are adequately protected before any public disclosure.

d. Gender dimension in CDE activities

Our Communication and Dissemination Plan is designed to be gender-sensitive, ensuring inclusive representation and equitable access to project information and activities. All visual and written materials will reflect gender diversity, avoiding stereotypes and promoting balanced portrayals of roles and contributions. For example, when showcasing project outcomes, we will highlight success stories from both women and men involved in REMORA, and ensure gender balance in speakers and participants at dissemination events. These efforts aim to foster inclusivity and amplify diverse perspectives in all project communications.

e. Reporting procedures

As part of the EU contractual requirements, all scientific publications, dissemination activities and communication activities are reported as part of the continuous reporting of the project in the EC Funding and Tender Opportunities Portal.

Data on all communication, dissemination and exploitation activities will be collected through REMORA CDE Reporting Log by RUIZIA (Inspired from the EmpowerUs log developed by ERINN) and uploaded to the portal by ARDITI. To successfully manage this reporting, all partners are encouraged to routinely update the log which will be shared in the shared folder.

The log is available [here](#).

2. Targeted Stakeholders

Our CDE Plan has been developed using a systemic approach to ensure alignment with the project's overarching objectives. The diversity of target groups reflects a deliberate effort to engage all critical stakeholders whose involvement is essential to achieve meaningful and lasting impact. Each group has been carefully identified based on its potential to contribute to or benefit from the project's outcomes. This approach allows us to prioritize key stakeholders effectively while maintaining the flexibility to address the interconnections and synergies between groups, thereby ensuring a coherent and strategic dissemination effort. A summary of the target audiences is provided in Figure 1, with further details elaborated in dedicated sections.

Figure 2. Key target audiences for REMORA outputs

3. Project Description

The « project description » includes key facts and messages tailored for communication purposes to raise awareness and build interest. It enables REMORA's stakeholders to present the project in a common way with harmonized information regarding:

- Project identity and presentation summaries
- Project's objectives, pathway and cases studies
- Consortium & teams (individuals) and Governance
- Activities, Results, Expected Outcomes and impacts

The project details are summarized into a « Project Description Notice » available in *Annex 1*.

4. Main communication tools and channels

a. Branding material

REMORA's branding materials are developed throughout the project and are available in [REMORA's shared folder](#).

⊗ Brand Identity

The brand identity for the project is carefully crafted to ensure recognition and consistency across all communication channels. Key elements include:

- **Visual Identity:** The project's visual identity provides a professional look and feel, reflecting the project's core values and objectives. Elaborated by ARDITI, the REMORA logo combines modern design elements to reflect the project's themes of innovation, connectivity, and competitiveness. ARDITI also provided a « Logo kit » to help partners in the use of the elements, with specifications in terms of variations of the logo, color palette, typography, favicon and icon declinations for digital use. The Visual identity and logo Kit are detailed and available [here](#).

Figure 3. REMORA logo

- **Catchy Slogans and Taglines:** Engaging and memorable messages will be developed to convey the essence of the project to diverse audiences effectively, fighting against preconceived ideas on R&I in the Outermost regions.

Examples of slogans:

"European Outermost regions: where boundaries inspire breakthroughs in Ocean science"

"Frontiers of Europe, frontiers of Knowledge — advancing marine science from the outermost regions"

"Geographically distant, scientifically vital: the Outermost regions inspiring Europe's ocean research & innovation »"

Examples of tagline:

Through REMORA - a EU funded project, 3 Ocean research centers from the Outermost regions enhance their Excellence & Competitiveness and become Horizon Europe

- **Project Templates:** REMORA's team have prepared templates for presentations, documents, and deliverables to ensure uniformity in project communication. All branding identity material are available online in a [shared folder here](#).

⊗ Print & Multimedia

To enhance visibility and engagement, a variety of print and multimedia materials will be developed, including:

- **Project Fact Sheet:** A concise and informative 1 page document summarizing the project's objectives, key activities, and expected impacts.
- **Project Poster:** Designed for public events, the poster will visually highlight the project's main messages and achievements.
- **Digital Infographic:** A dynamic infographic, updated throughout the project's lifecycle, will showcase progress and key outcomes in an accessible format.
- **Slide Presentation:** A 5 slide presentation summarizing the project's ambition, objectives, and expected outcomes for diverse stakeholders.
- **Expert Testimonials:** Videos and presentations featuring high-level experts from the project team and Advisory Board (AB) members will lend credibility and showcase the expertise driving the project. These multimedia materials will be tailored for maximum impact on various platforms.

⊗ Joint internationalization strategy promotion kit

To specifically advertise the joint internationalization strategy developed under REMORA Task 2.3, the key expertise of CITEB, OOM and OKEANOS and their respective regions in EU major networks (during WP3), ARDITI will also elaborate a promotion kit which will notably capitalize on the R&I portfolio (REMORA Deliverable 2.1) and other available communication materials produced in the 3 regions. This promotion kit will be made available to all partners to facilitate a coordinated and coherent communication, and it will be disseminated through institutional communication channels, presentations in R&I seminars and B2B meetings.

As part of REMORA's task 5.2, the development of this kit will start in 2025.

b. Digital platforms

⊗ Website

The REMORA project website has been thoughtfully designed to serve as both a platform for engagement and a showcase of the unique strengths and potential of stakeholders in Europe's outermost regions (ORs). It addresses a critical challenge faced by research centers in these territories: overcoming perceptions of being less endowed, less visible, and lacking excellence or space for cutting-edge research. By highlighting the natural and strategic assets, innovation capacity, and contributions of OR stakeholders, the website fosters pride within these communities while simultaneously attracting interest and collaboration from leading research centers worldwide.

Key Features:

Telling a Compelling Story: Through visuals, slogans and case studies, the website presents a narrative of creativity and untapped potential, reframing ORs not as peripheral, but as central to addressing pressing global issues.

Showcasing Excellence in Outermost Regions: The website emphasizes the strengths, achievements, and unique perspectives of OR research centers, demonstrating their critical role in advancing scientific

knowledge and addressing global challenges, such as biodiversity, climate resilience, and ocean sciences.

Attracting Collaboration: Tailored content highlights the mutual benefits of partnerships, showcasing the resources, expertise, and opportunities available in ORs, thus positioning these regions as attractive and valuable research collaborators.

Engagement and Accessibility: With intuitive design and accessible language, the site invites stakeholders from diverse backgrounds to explore, connect, and engage with the REMORA project and its vision.

Strategic Role:

As a cornerstone of the CDE plan, the REMORA website serves as a hub for communication, dissemination, and engagement with stakeholders, showcasing the project’s objectives, methodology, activities, and outcomes. By fostering connections and promoting the project’s outputs with dedicated sections, it contributes to the sustainability and long-term impact of REMORA’s results.

Target Audience:

The REMORA website has been designed to serve a diverse audience, including researchers, policymakers, businesses, and the general public, in the Outermost regions and in Continental EU. Content is structured to cater to varying levels of expertise, with accessible language and visuals ensuring inclusivity and gender sensitive communication.

Visual Identity:

We will use the REMORA logo as a watermark and apply brand-compliant visuals, including infographics, photos, and videos.

Figure 4. REMORA’s website homepage preview

⊗ Social Media

The REMORA social media strategy aims to enhance visibility, engage diverse audiences, and foster a sense of community around REMORA's initiatives in La Réunion, Madeira, and the Azores.

This strategy is structured around the following items:

Platform:

- Primary Platform: CSA-REMORA LinkedIn account (for professional and policy engagement).
- Support Channels: Partners' social media accounts for content amplification :
 - o @ARDITI - Agência Regional para o Desenvolvimento da Investigação, Tecnologia e Inovação
 - o @citeb
 - o @Observatório Oceânico da Madeira,
 - o @Okeanos - Institute of Marine Sciences
 - o @ DTU - Technical University of Denmark
 - o @ERINN Innovation

Content focus:

- Researcher stories highlighting key contributors and scientific achievements.
- Project milestones, including funding successes and technical breakthroughs.
- Policy engagement updates and community-focused stories.
- Educational content about marine research and funding processes.

Key messaging principles:

- Authentic: share real stories, research breakthroughs, and project milestones.
- Impact-driven: highlight research results and societal benefits.
- Inclusive: communicate effectively with both scientific and general audiences.
- Collaborative: acknowledge partner contributions to strengthen shared narratives.

Posting guidelines:

- Consistency: ensure all posts align with REMORA's key messaging framework.
- Frequency: linkedIn: 2-3 posts/reposts per week
- Engagement: actively respond to comments and messages to foster dialogue.
- Monitoring: use analytics tools to measure engagement, follower growth, and reach.

Visual Identity:

- use the REMORA logo as a watermark;
- apply brand-compliant visuals, including infographics, photos, and videos.

Best practices:

- Tagging: mention partner organizations in posts to amplify reach.
- Hashtags: strategic mix of project-specific and broader hashtags, including:
 - Project-specific: **#REMORAProject, #OutermostRegions, #PathwaystoSynergies**
 - Research-oriented: **#MarineResearch, #ScientificInnovation, #EUResearch, #HorizonEU, #ResearchImpactEU, #EUIInnovation**

- **Involving EU institutions** : @European Research Executive agency ; @EU Science, Research and Innovation
- Environmental impact: #OceanScience, #MarineSustainability, #ClimateAction.
- Community & advocacy: #SaveOurSeas, #OceanConservation.
- Event-based: relevant event hashtags like #WorldOceansDay #EuropeanMaritimeDay when appropriate.

Collaboration: partners are encouraged to share REMORA updates on their platforms.

c. External newsletters

As a tool for collaboration, visibility, and inspiration, we will release newsletters periodically throughout the project to inform both the partnership and interested stakeholders about key updates and opportunities. These newsletters will ensure stakeholders remain informed and motivated to contribute to the project's success, strengthen connections among participants and inspire collaboration.

Each edition will feature:

- Project achievements
- Calls for Interest & event invitations: Opportunities for stakeholders to engage with ongoing activities
- Updates from the Coordination Team: Summarizing progress across work packages to keep everyone aligned.
- "Hope" Stories: Inspiring narratives from institutions, sharing noteworthy developments from participating organizations, such as new European projects and illustrating how the project contributes to their growth and impact in the broader European research landscape or strategic

REMORA team will provide a maximum of 5 newsletters, with a minimum of 1 per year.

To ensure an efficient emailing management and help grow the list of recipients, we will use an email marketing platform (such as MailChimp) which will be also connected to the project website.

d. General public outreach contents

To engage the public and media and amplify the project's visibility and impacts, we will create tailored content that highlights the project's contributions to regional development and prosperity.

- **Press Communication Content:**

Press releases will be prepared during key milestones, such as the two symposia and the final conference. These press releases will outline major achievements, summarize the discussions and outcomes of these events, and emphasize the broader relevance of the project's results to stakeholders and the general public.

- **Science Communication Content:**

To ensure the project's ambition and results are accessible and engaging to non-specialist audiences, we will develop tailored science communication materials which can be used for:

- Public conference
- Science-Society actions

These will translate complex scientific concepts into clear, compelling narratives, emphasizing the real-world impact of our work on ocean and marine science.

▪ **Ocean Literacy Leaflet:**

Fostering a deeper connection between local communities and the ocean is crucial for the sustainability of Ocean Science in the Outermost regions. To help R&I stakeholders to promote ocean-related issues in their respective communities, we will produce an ocean literacy leaflet which will detail the significance of ocean literacy in partner regions, highlight ongoing initiatives, and propose actionable steps to enhance understanding and engagement with the ocean. This material will serve as a resource to give R&I stakeholders matter to educational and advocacy activities.

e. Events

The project includes the organization of numerous events targeting diverse stakeholder groups. These events provide valuable opportunities to implement and enhance CDE activities. Table 4 outlines the project's events along with their primary target audiences. Details on how each event will be tailored to engage specific stakeholder groups can be found in the dedicated stakeholder sections later in this document (Sections III to X).

In addition to the project's own events, the team will actively conduct CDE activities during regional events, scientific conferences, and policy summits. These external engagements are further detailed in the relevant sections within the dedicated stakeholder chapters of this document.

Legend of table 4:

SG: Stakeholder group

SG1: Consortium partners and staff members

SG2: Advisory board members

SG3: Outermost citizens and general public

SG4: European marine R&I institutions

SG5: Other R&I organizations in La Reunion, Madeira and Dos Açores

SG6: R&I policy-makers from the outermost regions

SG7: R&I organisations and policy-makers from widening territories

SG8: EU R&I policy working groups and EU institutions

Table 4. Overview of REMORA events and target stakeholder groups

WP events	Month	SG1	SG2	SG3	SG4	SG5	SG6	SG7	SG8
WP1 (Organizations strategy and individual capacities):									
- Study visit at DTU	3	X			X				
- 1 st and 2 nd series of internal workshops	6, 10	X							
- Online mutual learning event 1 and 2	7, 11	X							
- WP1 trainings	12→33								
WP2 (Joint internalisation strategy):									
- WP2 Joint workshop for R&I assets 1 & 2	7, 11		X		X				
- WP2 Joint workshop for EU intelligence 3, 4, 5, 6	12→13								
- Joint internationalization strategy webinar	15	X	X		X		X	X	X
WP3 (Networking activities):									
- Symposium at La Reunion (M16)	16	X	X	X	X	X		X	
- WP3 Joint webinar 1, 2, 3	18, 23 ; 30								
- Symposium at Madeira (M21)	21	X	X	X	X	X		X	
- WP3 Horizon Europe Incubator hackathons					X				
- WP3 networking preparatory meetings	TBD	X				X			
WP4 (Systematization and replicability):									
- Policy workshop 1, 2, 3, 4	17, 19, 28, 29		X				X		
- Regional workshops (one in La Reunion and one in Madeira)	25→26					X			
WP5 (Communication & Dissemination):									
- Communication team Workshops (M3 → M6)	3→6								
- Dissemination webinar for OR R&I policymakers (M31)	31		X				X		X
- Dissemination webinar for Widening R&I organizations (M32)	32		X					X	X
- Dissemination event at final conference (M33)	33		X		X	X	X	X	X
WP6 (Management & coordination)									
- KOM, 8 Project Meetings	6, 11, 15, 20, 25, 29, 33	X							
- REMORA general assembly during Project Meeting n°3, 6, 8	11, 33								
- REMORA final conference	33		X	X					

III. STAKEHOLDER GROUP 1: CONSORTIUM PARTNERS AND STAFF MEMBERS

1. Who are they?

REMORA consortium is composed of 6 partners whose staff members can be divided into 2 groups: people directly involved in the project and those who are not.

Organization	Staff directly involved	Total staff
ARDITI		
- Management / support	3	
- OOM	2	
- Other Units / platform	0	
- Regional Directorate For The Sea (associated)	1	
RUIZIA	2	2
CITEB	4	8
Univ. dos Açores		
- OKEANOS	4	150
- University Management	0	
- Other institutes/groups	0	
DTU Aqua		
- Institute Management	0	
- Research secretariat	2	
- Section for Oceans & Arctic	1	
- Other 9 sections	0	
- Students	0	
ERINN	1	
Total	20	
% target	100% becoming ambassadors	

2. Objectives & key messages

Why should we involve them ?

- To foster positive perception of Horizon Europe programmes, international cooperation and Excellence for ERA
- To build trust in and sense of pride for REMORA
- To strengthen organizational cohesion, and ensure the broader team feels valued, even if not directly engaged
- To inspire indirect support and interest, and encourage collaboration across departments
- To ease the future integration of project outcomes

What are our CDE objectives ?

- To make consortium staff members « **ambassadors** » of
- Horizon europe programme,
 - Outermost Regions Ocean Science
 - REMORA

Examples of Key message:

Thanks to Horizon Europe, REMORA fosters the development of 3 Outermost marine centers - OOM, CITEB, OKEANOS - strengthening global Ocean Science and driving prosperity in the outermost regions of EU.

How will we do that ?

By keeping people informed about goals, progress, and impacts, with regular updates.

3. Tools, channels, activities

- Main material
 - Project description notice
 - Project Print & Multimedia
 - Project Results, Deliverables
 - Excellence for ERA roadmap
 - R&I portfolio
 - Joint internationalization strategy
 - Specific documents
 - Training materials
 - Call for Networking fellowships
 - Call for interest for the Horizon Europe incubator Hackathons
- Main Channels
 - REMORA website
 - REMORA LinkedIn & partners' LinkedIn
 - Newsletters
 - Direct emails
 - Partners' internal meetings
- Main events
 - WP1 internal workshops
 - WP1 trainings
 - WP2 internal workshops
 - WP3 symposia
 - WP3 networking preparatory meetings
 - WP3 Horizon Europe Incubator hackathons
 - REMORA general assembly
 - Dedicated online session during REMORA final conference

4. Timeframe

- Engaging with :
 - M6 : Website launch
 - M6 → M8 : WP1 internal workshops

- Keeping engagement during project with :
 - ❑ M8 : Portfolio publication
 - ❑ M11 : ERA Roadmap publication
 - ❑ M12 : 1st Newsletter
 - ❑ M12 → M30 : Capacity building activities
 - ❑ M15 : joint internationalization strategy
 - ❑ M16 & M21 : REMORA symposia
 - ❑ M17 → M36 : Launch of the networking fellowships
 - ❑ M17 → M36 : Launch of the Horizon Europe incubator
 - ❑ M18 : 2nd Newsletter
 - ❑ M24 : 3rd Newsletter
 - ❑ M30 : 4th Newsletter
 - ❑ M33 : General assembly meeting during the final conference
 - ❑ M36 : 5th Newsletter

IV. STAKEHOLDER GROUP 2 : REMORA ADVISORY BOARD MEMBERS

1. Who are they ?

REMORA's Advisory Board consists of a diverse group of high-level experts, including internationally recognized personalities who were selected for their deep knowledge and experience :

- Experts in **Ocean Sciences**, with a focus on sustainable marine research, climate change impacts, and the blue economy.
- Authorities in **R&I systems**, including their strategic development, innovation policies, and integration into global frameworks like Horizon Europe.
- Specialists in **funding synergies**, who understand the complexities of mixing multiple EU funding sources for R&I

The AB members bring invaluable external perspectives and ensure that the project remains aligned with the latest scientific developments and Horizon Europe's strategic priorities. Their expertise in both scientific content and funding strategies will help optimize project outcomes and improve its visibility and sustainability within the wider European context.

2. Objectives & key messages

Why should we involve them ?

Their involvement will enhance the project scientific excellence, societal relevance, and funding success.

What are our CDE objectives ?

→ Engage the members to ensure strategic guidance and provision of expertise

Examples of Key message:

As trusted advisors, your contribution is crucial to enhance REMORA's credibility, visibility and sustainability

How will we do that ?

3. Tools, channels, activities

- Main material
 - Project description notice
 - Project Print & Multimedia
 - Project Results and deliverables
 - WP1 : Excellence for ERA guidelines, Excellence for ERA roadmaps
 - WP2 : R&I portfolio, Joint internationalization strategy
 - WP3 : Horizon Europe incubator operational guide
 - WP4 : Policy Lab Notice, Policy briefs
 - Specific documents
 - A dedicated section in REMORA's website
- Main Channels
 - Direct emails

- Dedicated AB meetings
 - REMORA website
 - REMORA LinkedIn & partners' LinkedIn
 - Newsletters
- Main events
 - WP3 symposia
 - REMORA general assembly
 - REMORA final conference
- 4. Timeframe**
- Engaging with :
 - Direct emails at M1,2, 3
 - 1st AB meeting M4
 - 2nd AB Meeting M6
 - Project website launch at M8
 - Keeping engagement during project with :
 - M8 : Portfolio publication
 - M11 : ERA Roadmaps publication
 - M12 : 1st Newsletter
 - M15 : joint internationalization strategy
 - M16 & M21 : REMORA symposia
 - M17 → M36 : Launch of the networking fellowships
 - M17 → M36 : Launch of the Horizon Europe incubator
 - M18 : 2nd Newsletter
 - M24 : 3rd Newsletter
 - M30 : 4th Newsletter
 - M33 : General assembly meeting during the final conference
 - M36 : 5th Newsletter

V. STAKEHOLDER GROUP 3 : OUTERMOST CITIZENS AND GENERAL PUBLIC

1. Who are they ?

Considering the size and scope of REMORA, our DEC mobilizes existing channels in La Réunion, Madeira and the Azores such as social media accounts, local press and public events. Since the access to such channels is socially determined, REMORA will target specific categories of the general population :

- People interested in science, research and innovation who either follow partner organizations on social media and newsletters or regularly read regional information sources (such as newspapers and websites) and have enough time and resources to pay interest to REMORA' activities.
- People interested in regional development challenges
- People interested in ocean and/or science literacy who regularly organize or attend public events.
- Students who are already present on the campuses where the symposia will be held.

2. Objectives & key messages

Why should we involve them :

- Despite political claims to become “knowledge hubs”, the outermost regions invest a very limited share of their GDP in knowledge-intensive activities. Moreover, the quest for short-term economic growth frequently blinds the critical importance of basic and applied research, notably to address social issues. Promoting the benefits of R&I activities is thus essential to overcome established bias and raise the investment in science.
- In a period of high uncertainty and global ecological crisis, the outermost regions face the challenge to reduce their dependencies and vulnerabilities, and to rely more on their domestic assets; Yet, the objectives to reconcile ocean exploitation and conservation often remain a form of wishful thinking and lack concrete examples. Promoting tangible examples of activities that support local communities without impacting the ecosystems they rely on is thus decisive.

What are our CDE objectives:

→ To turn targeted participants into « **promotors** » of :

- The decisive importance to invest in research and innovation in the Outermost Regions.
- The need to adopt knowledge-based management of coastal and maritime areas to secure local communities.
- The capacity of the outermost regions not only to host but to conduct world-class research and innovation projects and to effectively contribute to tackling global challenges.

Examples of key messages :

“Discover the power of Ocean science to strengthen resilience and drive prosperity in our outermost regions”

3. Tools, channels, activities

- Main material
 - Project description notice
 - Project Print & Multimedia
 - Project Fact Sheet
 - Project Poster
 - Digital Infographic
 - Videos on Expert Testimonials (project team and Advisory Board members)
 - General public content highlighting REMORA's contribution to regional prosperity and Excellence of Science in Outermost regions
 - Press Communication Content
 - Science Communication Content
 - Ocean Literacy Leaflet
- Main Channels
 - Project website
 - Social Media
 - Communication events (see below)
 - Press strategy
 - Press conference at REMORA symposium in La Reunion, sept 2025
 - Press conference at REMORA symposium in Madeira, Feb 2026
 - Press releases for the publication of REMORA Portfolio, the Joint Internationalization strategy, & at final conference in Brussels, May 2027
- Main events
 - Within REMORA's symposia in La Reunion and Madeira
 - Public conference
 - Seminars targeting students to promote exchanges between ORs
 - Public Communication events
 - Açores/Madeira :
 - SciComPT Apr 2025 in Madeira² & 2026
 - MacaroNight 2025³
 - La Reunion : Fête de la science⁴ 2025 & 2026, June Day of blue Economy⁵

4. Timeframe

- Engaging with :
 - M8 (January 25) : Social Media for REMORA's website launch
- Keeping engagement during project with :
 - M9 : Press release for Portfolio publication
 - M11 : SciComPT 2025 in Madeira

²SciComPT is a Portuguese network and annual congress focused on advancing science communication and informal science education. <https://scicom.pt/home>

³ MacaroNight is part of the European Researchers' Night initiative, uniting the Macaronesian archipelago to promote scientific culture and inspire future researchers.

⁴ La Fête de la Science is an annual event across France and its territories, including La Réunion, aimed at making science accessible to all through interactive workshops, exhibitions, and discussions that showcase various scientific disciplines and innovations.

⁵ The Blue Economy Day in La Réunion, held every June, promotes sustainable marine development by connecting stakeholders in sectors like fisheries, aquaculture, and marine renewable energy, focusing on innovation and regional collaboration

- M13 : Blue Economy Day at La Reunion
- M15 : Press release for joint internationalization strategy
- M16/17 : Macaronight in Madeira / Açores and Fête de la science in La Reunion
- M16 :
 - Press conference/public conference /students seminar during Symposia in La Reunion
 - Press release in Madeira
 - Press release in the Açores
- M21 :
 - Press conference/public conference /students seminar during Symposia in Madeira
 - Press release in La Reunion
 - Press release in the Açores
- M28/29 : Macaronight in Madeira / Açores and Fête de la science in La Reunion
- M33 : Press release for the final conference

VI. STAKEHOLDER GROUP 4 : EUROPEAN MARINE R&I INSTITUTIONS

1. Who are they ?

This group of stakeholders represents a diverse and interconnected network of organizations advancing marine science, innovation, and policy.

Types	List	Contact
<p>(1) Collaborative Research and Innovation networks and initiatives : These organizations and initiatives focus on fostering cooperation and innovation in marine and ocean research across Europe.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - EuroMarine: https://www.euromarineconsortium.eu/ - European Marine Board: https://www.marineboard.eu/ - ICES (International Council for the Exploration of the Sea): https://www.ices.dk/ - Marine Biodiversity Observation Network Europe: https://www.mbon.eu/ - JPI Oceans: https://www.jpi-oceans.eu/ - Sustainable Blue Partnership: https://sustainablebluepartnership.org/ - Mission « Ocean, Seas, and Waters » Initiative : link 	<p>Euromarine (AB) FRCT (AB)</p>
<p>(2) Specialized Marine Research Infrastructures and Data networks : These institutions provide advanced tools, facilities and data for high-level marine and ocean research.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - EMSO ERIC, European Multidisciplinary Seafloor and Water Column Observatory, https://emso.eu - Euro-Argo ERIC, European Research Infrastructure for the Observation of the Ocean, https://www.euro-argo.eu - EMBRC-ERIC, European Marine Biological Resource Centre, https://www.embrc.eu - JERICO, Joint European Research Infrastructure for Coastal Observatories, https://www.jerico-ri.eu 	<p>EMSO ERIC (AB)</p>
<p>(3) Horizon Europe champions : These leading institutions are pivotal in advancing marine and ocean research under Horizon Europe, as coordinators or participants.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - DTU Aqua (Denmark) - GEOMAR (Germany) - MARUM (Germany) - University of Bergen (Norway) - CMMI (Cyprus) <p>This list will be updated under WP2 where we will analyze the participation from CORDIS dashboards.</p>	<p>DTU AQUA ERINN</p>

2. Objectives & key messages

Why should we involve them :

→ to increase active cooperation between the Outermost regions (Azores, Madeira, La Reunion) and EU champions

→ to raise the European reputation of CITEB, OOM and OKEANOS and promote the assets of La Réunion, Madeira and the Azores to join Horizon Europe consortia

What are our CDE objectives:

→ REMORA's project outcomes can provide valuable contributions in the form of data, policy recommendations, new methodologies and technology solutions to bridge the knowledge gap in global ocean science due to under-investigated research fields in the Atlantic and Indian ocean

→ In return, REMORA can benefit from their scientific expertise, data resources, and collaborative opportunities to ensure the project's results have long-term, broad-reaching impact across European marine science and policy.

→ REMORA's key assets will be developed under WP2 during the preparation of the Portfolio of "R&I assets".

Examples of key messages :

« Together La Réunion, Madeira and the Azores cover a wide range of marine habitats and offer world-class infrastructures and expertise for high quality, impactful research and innovation projects. They are ideal partners to increase the competitiveness of related Horizon Europe applications »

« Small & smart solutions for Global Ocean Observatory »

3. Tools, channels, activities

- Main material
 - Project description notice
 - Project Print & Multimedia
 - Project Fact Sheet
 - Digital Infographic
 - Videos on Expert Testimonials (project team and Advisory Board members)
 - Project Results and deliverables
 - WP2 : R&I portfolio, Joint internationalization strategy
 - WP3 : Horizon Europe proposals concepts
 - WP4 : Policy briefs
 - Specific documents
 - Call for interest for the Horizon Europe incubator Hackathons
- Main Channels
 - Project website
 - Social Media
 - Direct Invitations to REMORA's activities & events
 - Scientific networking through notably
 - ICES Science symposia
 - Euromarine events
 - EMB Science webinars
- Main events
 - Within REMORA
 - Symposia in La Reunion and Madeira
 - WP3 Horizon Europe Incubator hackathons

- Webinar promoting the Joint internationalization strategy (M15)
- Events/conferences as identified by REMORA's partners :
 - Copernicus Marine / One Ocean science : Nice, France | 4-6 June 2025
 - Ocean Sciences Meeting 2026 : Glasgow | 22-27 Feb 2026
 - European Maritime day : TBD
 - European Ocean Days: Brussels, Belgium| 3-7 March 2025

4. Timeframe

A specific action plan to engage these stakeholders will be prepared once the analysis of the main networks/institutions to engage will start under the WP2 framework (preparation of the Joint internationalization strategy).

VII. STAKEHOLDER GROUP 5 : OTHER R&I ORGANIZATIONS IN LA REUNION, MADEIRA AND THE AZORES

1. Who are they ?

This stakeholder group are organizations implementing Research and Innovation activities and located in one of the three outermost regions. It can be research centers, cluster, Universities, innovative companies which are mainly interested in ESIF fundings. This group is divided into 3 subgroups :

Targeted R&I organizations in La Réunion (8)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 3 marine centers: Centre d'Etudes et de découverte des tortues marines, Institut de Recherche pour le Développement, local antenna of IFREMER - 1 regional blue economy cluster : "Institut Bleu" - 2 innovation platforms: Biotechnology platform CYROI and CIRBAT - 1 University : Université de La Réunion - 1 marine Citizen-science organization : GLOBICE
Targeted R&I organizations in Madeira (9)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 1 Business cluster: Startup Madeira - 1 public research center: Calheta Mariculture Center - 1 regional policy maker : Regional Directorate of Environment and Sea - 1 University: University of Madeira - 3 Innovative companies running in the Ocean and Marine sector: Phytoalgae, madeBiotech, UBQ Madeira
Targeted R&I organizations in the Azores
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Regional Research and Innovation funding agency: FRCT - 1 University: Universidade dos Açores

2. Objectives & key messages

Why should we involve them :

The CITEB, OOM and OKEANOS case studies were designed to inspire other Research and Innovation organizations to overcome ESIF dependency and Horizon Europe reluctance. Through the promotion of the benefits and feasibility of their organizational transformation and European journey, REMORA will foster the internationalization of the 3 regional R&I systems.

What are our CDE objectives:

→ Empower other organizations to exploit the opportunities of ESIF/Horizon Europe synergies to support their long-lasting development and internationalization

Examples of key messages :

→ Scientist from REMORA should pass messages through videos : « Though ERDF provides a comfortable, easily accessible funding source, Horizon Europe offers more than money : access to high-end knowledge and technologies, international development opportunities, international recognition, talent attraction, etc. »

3. Tools, channels, activities

- Main material

- Project description notice
- Project Results and deliverables
 - WP1 : Guidelines for Excellence for ERA roadmap;
 - WP2 : R&I portfolio, Joint internationalization strategy
 - WP4 : Brief on the benefits of a Joint internationalization
- Specific documents
 - Videos Testimonials from Scientist from CITEB, OOM, OKEANOS
 - Call for interest for the Horizon Europe incubator Hackathons
- Main Channels
 - Project website
 - Social Media
 - WP4 events
 - Direct emails
- Main events
 - Within REMORA
 - Regional workshops 1 in La Reunion and 1 in Madeira M25/M26
 - WP3 Horizon Europe Incubator hackathons
 - Dissemination webinar for Widening R&I organizations (M32)
 - Events as identified by REMORA's partners :
 - At La Reunion a talk at « Jeudi du CYROI », a regular seminars organized by and at CYROI (Cyclotron Réunion Océan Indien - a multidisciplinary research platform based in La Réunion)
 - At Madeira : to be determined
 - At Açores : to be determined

4. Timeframe

- Engaging with :
 - M8 (January 25) : Social Media for REMORA's website launch
- Keeping engagement during project with :
 - M9 : Press release for Portfolio publication
 - M12 : 1st Newsletter
 - M15 : Press release for joint internationalization strategy
 - M16 & M21 : Press conference/public conference during Symposia in La Reunion and in Madeira
 - M17 → M36 : Launch of the networking fellowships
 - M17 → M36 : Launch of the Horizon Europe incubator
 - M18 : 2nd Newsletter
 - M20 : 1 talk « Jeudi du
 - M24 : 3rd Newsletter
 - M25/M26 : Regional workshops
 - M30 : 4th Newsletter
 - M36 : 5th Newsletter

VIII. STAKEHOLDER GROUP 6 : RESEARCH & INNOVATION POLICY-MAKERS FROM THE OUTERMOST REGIONS

1. Who are they ?

Research and Innovation (R&I) policy-makers in the Outermost Regions (ORs) play a central role in the structuration and internationalization of regional R&I systems through the regional strategies and plans. These stakeholders include entities :

- responsible for designing and implementing Smart Specialization Strategies (S3), which identify regional strengths and prioritize investments in R&I.
- managing allocations from the European Structural & Investment Funds (ESIF) dedicated to R&I

This group are composed of the R&I policymakers located in the 3 regions involved in REMORA – La Reunion, Madeira, the Açores (presented in table X) – as well as policymakers from the other 6 outermost regions.

Region	Institutions	S3 / ESIF	Contact
Regions involved in REMORA consortium			
La Reunion	Direction Recherche et Innovation (Regional council of La Reunion)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> S3	RUIZIA
	Direction FEDER (Regional council of La Reunion)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> ESIF	RUIZIA
	Agence interfonds de La Réunion	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> ESIF	RUIZIA
Madeira	Secretaria Regional de Educação, Ciência e Tecnologia (Regional Government of Madeira)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> S3	ARDITI
	Direção Regional de Planeamento e Fundos Estruturais (Regional Government of Madeira)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> ESIF	ARDITI
The Azores	Direção Regional da Ciência, Inovação e Desenvolvimento (Regional government of the Azores)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> S3	FRCT
	Direção Regional do Planeamento e Fundos Estruturais (Regional government of the Azores)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> ESIF	FRCT
	Fundo Regional da Ciência e Tecnologia (autonomous entity managed by the Regional government of the Azores)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> ESIF as intermediate body	FRCT
Regions outside of REMORA consortium			
The Canary islands	The Canary Islands Institute of Technology	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> S3	ARDITI
Guadeloupe	Conseil régional de Guadeloupe	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> S3 / <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> ESIF	RUIZIA
Martinique	Collectivité territoriale de Martinique	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> S3 / <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> ESIF	RUIZIA
Guyane	Collectivité territoriale de Guyane	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> S3 / <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> ESIF	RUIZIA
Mayotte	Conseil départemental de Mayotte	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> S3 / <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> ESIF	RUIZIA
Saint-Martin	Collectivité de Saint-Martin	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> S3 / <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> ESIF	RUIZIA

2. Objectives & key messages

Why should we involve them :

- to enhance R&I funding synergies at regional-level in outermost regions and develop pro-horizon Europe policy-framework in outermost regions
- for a better use of ESIF-funded infrastructure through ERA-oriented strategic development

- to increase weight of knowledge economy in GDP and employment of the Outermost Regions
- to increased international mobility from EU “central regions” to the Outermost Regions (brain drain)

What are our CDE objectives:

- to encourage them to use the results of REMORA and design funding-sensitive R&I policies

Examples of key messages :

« Reinforcing regional participation in Horizon Europe is an imperative to accelerate the transition toward knowledge economy and compensate the programmed reduction of ERDF subsidies. Substitution between these two funds is not a fatality but a consequence of regional policies. With proper ambition and methods, establishing such synergies is feasible and impactful and REMORA will ease the transition of R&I policies to reach this objective. »

« The Azores, La Réunion and Madeira are living-labs (or models) for the design and implementation of systematic synergies between ERDF and Horizon Europe. They provide operational organizational and policy-tools to overcome the substitution effect. »

« From synergy by opportunity to synergy by design »

3. Tools, channels, activities

- Main material
 - Project Print & Multimedia
 - Project Fact Sheet
 - Digital Infographic
 - Project Results and deliverables
 - WP1 : Guidelines for Excellence for ERA roadmap;
 - WP2 : R&I portfolio, Joint internationalization strategy
 - WP4 : Brief on the challenges, levers and policy tools for synergies at regional level
 - Specific documents
 - Videos Testimonials from directors/high level experts from CITEB, OOM, OKEANOS
- Main Channels
 - Project website
 - Social Media
 - WP4 events**
 - Direct emails**
- Main events

- ❑ Within REMORA
 - ❑ WP4 Policy workshops (M17, 19, 28, 29)
 - ❑ WP5 Webinar on Synergies in Outermost regions (M30)
- ❑ Events as identified by REMORA's partners :
 - ❑ RIS3 MAC network meetings⁶
 - ❑ Working group meetings of the comité de suivi of the Conference des présidents des RUP⁷

4. Timeframe

- Engaging with :
 - ❑ M8 (January 25) : Social Media / Direct Emails for REMORA's website launch
- Keeping engagement during project with :
 - ❑ M9 : Press release for Portfolio publication
 - ❑ M12 : 1st Newsletter
 - ❑ M15 : Press release for joint internationalization strategy
 - ❑ M16 & M21 : Press conference/public conference during Symposia in La Reunion and in Madeira
 - ❑ M17 → M29 : WP4 Policy workshops
 - ❑ M18 : 2nd Newsletter
 - ❑ M24 : 3rd Newsletter
 - ❑ M25/M26 : Regional workshops
 - ❑ M30 : 4th Newsletter
 - ❑ M36 : 5th Newsletter

⁶ [RIS3 MAC network](#) is a transregional Platform for cooperation support in the context of Smart Specialization in MAC areas.

⁷ [The Conférence des Présidents des Régions Ultrapériphériques](#) (CPRUP) serves as a key coordination and advocacy body for the nine outermost regions (RUP) of the European Union. The conference operates through joint positions, initiatives, and projects aimed at enhancing economic, social, and territorial cohesion for the RUPs within the EU framework. The Comité de Suivi of the CPRUP acts as an operational body supporting the conference. The Comité helps in preparing joint actions, liaising with EU institutions, and addressing technical matters relevant to the RUPs

IX. STAKEHOLDER GROUP 7 : R&I ORGANISATIONS AND POLICY-MAKERS FROM WIDENING TERRITORIES

1. Who are they ?

Widening territories under Horizon Europe designates countries and regions that have lower participation rates in EU R&I projects and require additional support to enhance their innovation capabilities. These include EU Member States, Associated Countries and Outermost regions (this subgroup is already targeted in previous sections).

Specifically, we have identified 3 subgroups :

Category	List	Contacts
(1) Members of the governance and Europe support offices of R&I organizations (Universities, Research centers, etc.) that participate little in Horizon Europe	Organizations involved in the 15 selected « pathways to synergies » projects	RUIZIA NCP WIDERA (network of the National Contact Points for Widening Participation and Spreading Excellence)
(2) Members of the governance and Europe support offices of R&I organizations with significant experience in Horizon Europe and funding synergies	Cyprus Marine & Maritime Institute (CMMI) Plataforma Oceánica de Canarias (PLOCAN)	RUIZIA
(2) Regional ESIF managing authorities and RIS3 responsible bodies in widening regions with the highest substitution effect between Horizon Europe and ESIF	PL92 Mazowiecki regionalny PL52 Opolskie PL72 Swietokrzyskie PL84 Podlaskie PL82 Podkarpackie PL43 Lubuskie PL61 Kujawsko-Pomorskie PL62 Warminsko-Mazurskie PL22 Slaskie PL42 Zachodniopomorskie PL81 Lubelskie PL51 Dolnoslaskie BG31 Severozapaden EL51 Anatoliki Makedonia, Thraki EL42 Notio Aigaio HU32 Észak-Alföld HU23 Dél-Dunántúl HU21 Közép-Dunántúl HU31 Észak-Magyarország RO41 Sud-Vest Oltenia RO31 Sud - Muntenia	ERRIN, European Regions Research and Innovation Network

2. Objectives & key messages

Why should we involve them :

- to encourage the willingness of widening R&I organizations to replicate REMORA pathways implemented by the 3 role models
- to motivate widening R&I Organizations to take part in the ERA and collaborate with EU R&I networks and communities
- to increase participation in the Horizon Europe programmes of widening organizations, notably SMES
- to capitalize on existing remarkable initiatives and practices to meliorate the tools supporting REMORA pathways → to systematize a pro-horizon Europe policy-framework in outermost & widening regions
- for a better use of ESIF-funded infrastructure through ERA-oriented strategic development
- to reduce locked-in syndrome with an increased amount of EU contribution from Horizon Europe and reduced economic dependence on structural funds of widening R&I organizations

What are our CDE objectives:

- to encourage them to use the results of REMORA and design funding-sensitive strategies (organizations) and R&I policies (policy-makers)

Examples of key messages :

« Reinforcing regional participation in Horizon Europe is an imperative to accelerate the transition toward knowledge economy and compensate the programmed reduction of ERDF subsidies. Substitution between these two funds is not a fatality but a consequence of regional policies. With proper ambition and methods, establishing such synergies is feasible and impactful and REMORA will ease the transition of R&I policies to reach this objective. »

« The Azores, La Réunion and Madeira are living-labs (or models) for the design and implementation of systematic synergies between ERDF and Horizon Europe. Thanks to REMORA, a Horizon Europe project, they provide operational organizational and policy-tools to overcome the substitution effect. »

« From synergy by opportunity to synergy by design »

3. Tools, channels, activities

- Main material
 - Project Print & Multimedia
 - Project Fact Sheet
 - Digital Infographic
 - Videos Testimonials from directors/high level experts from CITEB, OOM, OKEANOS
 - Project Results and deliverables
 - WP1 : three « Excellence for ERA » roadmaps

- WP1 : Guidelines for « Excellence for ERA »
 - WP2 : R&I portfolio, Joint internationalization strategy
 - WP3 : Horizon Europe proposals concepts
 - WP4 : Policy briefs
- Specific documents
 - Call for interest for the Horizon Europe incubator Hackathons
- Main Channels
 - Project website
 - Social Media
 - Specialized media : Science | Business⁸
- Main events
 - Within REMORA
 - Joint internationalization strategy webinar (M15)
 - Dissemination webinar for Widening R&I organizations (M32)
 - WP3 Horizon Europe Incubator hackathons (M18 → M36)
 - Events/conferences as identified by REMORA's partners :
 - NCP WIDERA⁹ meetings
 - European Regions Research and Innovation Network (ERRIN) policy working group

4. Timeframe

- Engaging with :
 - M8 (January 25) : Direct Emails for REMORA's website launch
- Keeping engagement during project with :
 - M12 : 1st Newsletter
 - M15 : Joint internationalization strategy webinar
 - M18 → M36 : Call for interest for the Horizon Europe incubator Hackathons
 - M18 : 2nd Newsletter
 - M24 : 3rd Newsletter
 - M30 : 4th Newsletter`
 - M32 : Dissemination webinar for Widening R&I organizations
 - M36 : 5th Newsletter

⁸ Science|Business is a European media and communications company which produces news, reports, and analysis on critical topics such as Horizon Europe, digital transformation, health innovation, and climate change. It also operates an influential network of universities, research organizations, businesses, and public institutions, fostering partnerships and knowledge exchange ; and organizes high-level conferences, workshops, and policy forums to address pressing issues in science and technology governance.

⁹ NCP WIDERA is the network of National Contact Points for Widening Participation & Spreading Excellence.

X. STAKEHOLDER GROUP 8 : EU R&I POLICY WORKING GROUPS AND EU INSTITUTIONS

1. Who are they ?

Within this last but not least group, we want to specifically target 4 institutions :

- **R&I and Cohesion Managing Authorities' Network (RIMA)**: A network that facilitates collaboration between managing authorities of EU Cohesion Policy and R&I stakeholders to better integrate research and innovation into regional development strategies.
- **Smart Specialization Community of Practice (S3 CoP)**: A platform fostering collaboration, sharing best practices, and enhancing the design and implementation of Smart Specialization Strategies (S3) to drive innovation-led regional growth.
- **Outermost Regions Unit DG REGIO** : the division of the European Commission's Directorate-General for Regional and Urban Policy, focusing on addressing the needs and challenges of the EU's outermost regions.
- **ERA Unit of DG RTD**: the unit within the Directorate-General for Research and Innovation tasked with advancing the European Research Area (ERA) by promoting cross-border collaboration and aligning national R&I policies with EU priorities.
- **Widening Unit of the European Research Executive Agency**: the unit implementing Horizon Europe's Widening Participation and Spreading Excellence actions, focusing on bridging R&I performance gaps across Europe

2. Objectives & key messages

Why should we involve them :

- To develop EU cohesion policy tools that integrate synergies recommendations
- To increase the recognition of the Outermost Regions as key locations to develop top-end Ocean-related research and innovation activities
- to increase weight of knowledge economy in GDP and employment of the Outermost Regions

What are our CDE objectives:

- To encourage the use of REMORA results in the preparation of the next Widening component under the FP10 and for the next cohesion policies.

Examples of key messages :

« Synergies in R&I funding are crucial for the Outermost regions. Reinforcing regional participation in Horizon Europe with the support of regional funds is an imperative to accelerate the transition toward a resilient knowledge-based economy. With proper ambition and methods, establishing such synergies is feasible and impactful and REMORA's tools will help the transition of R&I policies to reach this objective. »

« The Azores, La Réunion and Madeira are living-labs (or models) for the design and implementation of systematic synergies between ERDF and Horizon Europe. Thanks to REMORA, a Horizon Europe project, they provide operational organizational and policy-tools to overcome the substitution effect. »

3. Tools, channels, activities

- Main material
 - Project Print & Multimedia
 - Project Fact Sheet
 - Digital Infographic
 - Project Results and deliverables
 - WP1 : Three « Excellence for ERA » roadmaps
 - WP1 : « Excellence for ERA » guidelines
 - WP2 : R&I portfolio & Joint internationalization strategy
 - WP4 : Policy briefs
- Main Channels
 - Project website
 - Social Media
 - Specialized media : Science | Business¹⁰
- Main events
 - Within REMORA
 - Joint internationalization strategy webinar (M15)
 - Seminar on synergies during the final event in BXL (M33)
 - Events/conferences as identified by REMORA's partners :
 - 2026 R&I days
 - 2026 WIRE conference¹¹ in Poland (End of 2025)
 - EU presidency conferences (to be determined later)

4. Timeframe

- Engaging with :
 - M8 (January 25) : Direct Emails for REMORA's website launch
- Keeping engagement during project with :
 - M12 : 1st Newsletter
 - M15: Joint internationalization strategy webinar
 - M18: 2nd Newsletter
 - M24: 3rd Newsletter
 - M30: 4th Newsletter`
 - M33: Seminar on synergies during the final event in BXL
 - M36 : 5th Newsletter

¹⁰ Science|Business is a European media and communications company which produces news, reports, and analysis on critical topics such as Horizon Europe, digital transformation, health innovation, and climate change. It also operates an influential network of universities, research organizations, businesses, and public institutions, fostering partnerships and knowledge exchange ; and organizes high-level conferences, workshops, and policy forums to address pressing issues in science and technology governance.

¹¹ The Week of Innovative Regions in Europe is the main European policy forum for innovation and regional development. The event will gather actors active in the innovation and education ecosystem with the aim of improving science-based competitiveness.

XI. PLANNING OVERVIEW

Month	CDE activities	SG1: Consortium partners and staff members	SG2: Advisory board members	SG3: Outermost citizens and general public	SG4: European marine R&I institutions	SG5: Other R&I organizations in La Reunion, Madeira and Dos Açores	SG6: R&I policy- makers from the outermost regions	SG7: R&I organisations & policy- makers from widening territories	SG8: EU R&I policy working groups and EU institutions
M1/M3	KOM & Study visits	E							
M1 --> M4	AB set up		E						
M5 --> M8	WP1 internal workshops	E							
M8	Official Website launch	X	X	E		E	E	E	E
M8 / M9	Portfolio publication	X	X	X	E	X	X		
M11	ERA Roadmap publication	X	X						
M11	SciComPT 2025 in Madeira			X					
M12	1st Newsletter	X	X		X	X	X	X	X
M12--> M30	Capacity building activities	X							
M13	Blue Economy Day at La Reunion			X					
M15	Joint internationalization strategy	X	X	X	X	X		X	X
M16	REMORA symposium in La Reunion	X	X	X	X				
M16	Public conference in La Reunion during symposium					X	X		
M16/M17	Macaronight in Madeira / Açores and Fête de la science in La Reunion			X					
M17-->M36	Launch of the networking fellowships	X	X		X	X			
M17-->M36	Launch of the Horizon Europe incubator	X	X		X	X			
M17-->M36	Launch of the interregional policy lab & 1st policy workshop						X		
M18	2 nd Newsletter	X	X		X	X	X	X	X
M19	2nd interregional policy workshop						X		
M20	Local regional system communication					X	X		

M21	REMORA symposium in Madeira	X	X		X				
M21	Public conference in Madeira during symposium			X		X	X		
M24	3 rd Newsletter	X	X		X	X	X	X	X
M25/M26	Regional workshops					X	X		
M28/M29	3 rd & 4 th interregional policy workshop						X		
M28/M29	Macaronight in Madeira / Açores and Fête de la science in La Reunion			X					
M30	4 th Newsletter	X	X		X	X	X	X	
M32	Dissemination webinar for Widening R&I organizations		X			X		X	X
M33	General assembly during Final conference	X	X						
M33	Dissemination event at final conference			X	X		X		X
M36	5 th Newsletter	X	X		X	X	X	X	

E : Engagement

ANNEX 1 : Project Description Notice

a. Project identity :

This « bullet point » presentation of REMORA encapsulates the main info about the project in a very short way :

- Project title : Small fishes in a big pond
- Horizon Europe Coordination and Support Actions (CSA)
- Widening call « Pathways to synergies »
- Total budget : 1.2 M€
- Duration : June 2024 → May 2027
- Rank 1st on 33 submitted, total mark : 15 / 15

b. REMORA in short :

REMORA ambitions to **transform CITEB, OKEANOS and OOM** - 3 Ocean and Marine **ESIF-funded institutions** in La Réunion, Madeira and the Azores - **into Horizon Europe champions**.

To that end, REMORA will enhance their **competitiveness** (notably human resources, knowledge transfer and innovation capacities), **strategic positioning and connections with major EU networks** through a joint internationalization strategy.

REMORA will then use the successful transformation of these **3 role models** to lead other ESIF-oriented R&I organizations and policy-makers in Outermost and Widening Regions on the path to synergies.

c. REMORA summary :

The growing innovation divide across the European Union appears particularly detrimental to small and emerging regional research and innovation systems like the Outermost Regions¹² (OR). With limited resources, these regions struggle to reach the critical mass needed to build comparative advantages and become knowledge societies. Though the European Research Area (ERA) and the Framework Programme (FP) could compensate this marginalization through greater knowledge circulation, resources sharing and talents mobilities, the Outermost Regions present a limited participation in FP7 and Horizon 2020. This underutilization notably stems from the competing relations between European Structural & Investments Funds (ESIF) and the framework programs or “substitution effect”: many organizations and individuals prioritize easily accessible ESIF, decide not to apply to the FP and end up in “substitution trap” which isolates them from promising collaborations.

To move Outermost Regions’ R&I organizations and systems from substitution to synergies, REMORA ambitions to transform three Ocean and Marine ESIF-funded institutions in La Réunion, Madeira and the Azores into Horizon Europe champions: **CITEB** – the Technical Center for Blue Economy of La Reunion, **OKEANOS** – the Institute of Marine Sciences of the University of the Açores and **OOM** - the Oceanic Observatory of Madeira. To that end, REMORA will enhance their competitiveness (notably human resources, knowledge transfer and innovation capacities), strategic positioning and connections with major EU networks through a joint internationalization strategy with the support of **ARDITI** – the Regional Agency for the Development of Research, Technology and Innovation of Madeira, **RUIZIA** – the regional agency for Development of La Reunion, the Marine Institute of **Denmark Technical University** and **ERINN**, a Marine Impact & Innovation expert SME.

REMORA will then use the successful transformation of these 3 role models to lead other ESIF-oriented R&I organizations and policy-makers in Outermost and Widening Regions on the path to synergies.

d. REMORA objectives, pathway and case studies :

¹² The European Union (EU) counts nine outermost regions, which are integral part of the Union and geographically distant from the continent: Azores, Canaries, Guadeloupe, Guyana, Madeira, Mayotte, Martinique, Réunion and Saint Martin.

REMORA has 2 strategic objectives :

- 1) to strengthen the competitiveness and Horizon Europe participation of 3 Outermost Regions’ key regional Ocean research centres
- 2) to increase ESIF/Horizon Europe synergies in regional R&I systems suffering from high substitution effect

REMORA is based on three pillars organized as a pathway :

Figure 5: REMORA’s pathway

REMORA’s methodology is based on 3 case studies at 2 levels:

- Organizational : the 3 research organizations – CITEB, OOM, OKEANOS - reflect the diversity of organizational settings in terms of size, orientations, experience in Horizon Europe projects, dependency to structural funds (ESIF)
- Regional : The 3 regional Research & Innovation systems – La Reunion, Madeira, Açores - reflect a diversity of regional settings in terms of performance (Regional innovation indicators), regional participation in Horizon projects, regional R&I system’s dependency to ESIF.

A schematic overview of the three case studies is presented in the following figure.

Figure 6: REMORA’s case studies

e. REMORA Consortium & teams (individuals)

REMORA is implemented by a consortium of 7 entities represented 6 direct partners (and one associated one) as illustrated in Figure X and presented in the following paragraphs.

Figure 7: REMORA consortium composition

Coordinator : ARDITI is the Regional Agency for the Development of Research, Technology, and Innovation, located in Madeira (PT). It is an institution open to society, of an interdisciplinary nature, and focused on developing research and innovative solutions in the domains of the Ocean, Technology, and Health. Founded by the Regional Government of Madeira, the University of Madeira, and Madeiran R&I companies, ARDITI aims to support research activities, experimental development, technological dissemination, professional training, and technical scientific information. Its R&I activities aim to contribute to the modernization and development of the Autonomous Region of Madeira.

The Oceanic Observatory of Madeira - OOM is a R&I center led by ARDITI. Launched in January 2014, OOM gathers 15 regional partners, operating in the common field of Ocean Sciences and Blue Economy. OOM is dedicated to research and permanent monitoring of the Ocean, which aims at providing the region with marine resources evaluation and management and adequate means for its sustainable development. To do so, OOM develops consolidated historical data, observations, and forecasts in a common platform, and will soon provide a global ocean observing system able to deliver ocean forecasts and early warnings, climate projections, and assessments, contributing to monitoring and protect the ocean health, creating a Madeira Digital Ocean space.

Team involved in REMORA:

Dr. Rui Caldeira (M), president of ARDITI and OOM

Lúcio Quintal (M), MSc, Senior project manager, REMORA project coordinator

Catia Jardim (W), MSc, Projects Office, REMORA financial manager

Dr. Carlos Lucas (M), Post-doc working for the Operational Centre of OOM

Website: <https://www.arditi.pt/pt/>

RUIZIA is a research SME from La Reunion specializing in Peripheries regional development. RUIZIA ambitions to empower peripheral communities for a knowledge-based, ecological, socially-inclusive prosperity. It produces knowledge on the Innovation divide within the European Research Area and assists local stakeholders (authorities, researchers, NGOs, CSO) to develop fruitful R&I cooperations at EU Level.

Team involved in REMORA:

Dr Philippe Holstein (M), PhD in institutional economics, Director of RUIZIA, Scientific coordinator of REMORA.

Dr Evelyne Tarnus (W), PhD in Biology, President of RUIZIA, Impacts and Dissemination manager of REMORA.

CITEB develops R&I projects in marine biotechnologies, sustainable fisheries, marine ecology and aquaculture. It offers expertise in sampling, field and lab analyses for public and private agencies, and foster new businesses opportunities in the field of Blue Economy through development and technology transfer support programmes targeting private companies.

Team involved in REMORA:

Dr Alina Tunin-Ley (W), PhD in marine biology, expert in microalgae valorization, responsible of the Biotech Unit, REMORA's correspondent.

Dr Jean Turquet (M), PhD in environmental toxicology, CITEB director, responsible of the Marine Toxicology Unit.

Dr Perrine Mangion (W), PhD in biogeochemistry, responsible of the Marine Environment Unit.

Dr Evgeny Romanov (M), PhD in marine biology, responsible of the Fisheries Unit.

Website: <https://citeb.re/>

OKEANOS is the institute of Marine Science of the University of the Azores, a public higher education institution located in the Autonomous Region of the Azores. Using its mid-Atlantic strategic position, OKEANOS conducts leading research and education to advance the understanding of the deep-sea and the open ocean, promoting the sustainable blue economy and management of marine ecosystems for the benefit of the society and the environment. OKEANOS members created a global network with over 280 active collaborations from 180 research institutions and are players in several international organizations (e.g., CBD, OSPAR, ICCAT, ICES), networks (Ocean Tracking Network, InterRidge, DOSI, INDEEP, CHESS), and review panels and expert groups. OKEANOS is highly involved in outreach activities to the general public, schools, young students and local industries.

Team involved in REMORA:

Dr Gui Menezes (M), the director of the OKEANOS, REMORA's correspondent

Dr Filipe Porteiro (M), OKEANOS Subdirector, REMORA's correspondent

Sandra Silva (W), Técnica Superior, REMORA's correspondent

Dr Ana Colaço (W), Dr Eva Giacomello (W), Dr. Ricardo Santos (M), senior researchers

Diana Catarino (W), junior researcher

Website: <https://www.oceanos.uac.pt/>

DTU, The Technical University of Denmark (DTU) is a leading self-governed university excelling in science and technology research. DTU Aqua specializes in sustainable use of marine and freshwater resources, conducts Danish national monitoring on fisheries, and supports the EU Marine Strategy

Framework Directive (MSFD). Its research spans ecosystem interactions, oceanography, climate, ocean biogeochemistry, aquaculture, fish and shellfish diseases, fisheries technology, and marine modeling. With significant experience coordinating Horizon projects, presently SEAWISE, SeaQUESTER, B-USEFUL, MISSION ATLANTIC and ProtectFish. The institute actively lobbies for EU calls, contributes to drafts, and coordinates proposal responses.

Team involved in REMORA:

Prof. Patrizio Mariani, Coordinator of Horizon2020 MISSION ATLANTIC

Dr Kirsten Thomsen, Head of Research Secretariat

Dr Ivo Grigorov, Fundraiser & Open science expert, REMORA's correspondent

ERINN Innovation is a knowledge-based company that partners with organisations to guide impactful Research & Innovation and deliver a sustainable future. As a partner in EU projects, ERINN specialises in leading work packages focused on communication dissemination and knowledge transfer, ensuring impactful and effective project outcomes across sectors and funding programmes. Leveraging a deep understanding of the EU-funding space, ERINN offers a comprehensive suite of proposal support services, including training, workshops, and direct assistance with proposal development.

Team involved in REMORA:

Sarah Sarsfield, Senior Project Officer

Website: <https://erinn.eu/>

f. Project governance

The governance of REMORA is composed of

- the Coordination Team with :

Lucio Quintal, project coordinator, from ARDITI	Philippe Holstein, scientific coordinator, from RUIZIA
Catia Jardim, financial manager, from ARDITI	Evelyne Tarnus, Impacts and dissemination manager, from RUIZIA

- the Steering Committee consisting of representatives of all partners in charge of project implementation planification and monitoring
- the Partner Assembly with one vote per partner as the ultimate decision-making body.

REMORA has also set up an advisory board which comprises qualified personalities, experts in Ocean Sciences, R&I systems and Synergies who will provide :

- independent advice and feedback on methodology tools and deliverables,
- guidance on ethical, gender, and open science dimensions for the project itself
- networking opportunities
- project results dissemination channels
- strategic advice on funding sources, to ensure REMORA's objectives and sustainability.

The composition and expertise of the Advisory board members are presented in the table X.

Table X : title of the table

Name	Profile
Dr. Luz Paramio	Dr. Luz Paramio is an Ocean Governance expert with 20 years of experience and a member of the Executive Board of the Regional Science and Technology Fund (FRCT) of the Azores Regional Government, responsible for the Research and Innovation Programs . She has contributed to 40 EU projects and has coordinated several OR's European Projects on the Maritime Affairs domain . She has represented the Azores actively in the Ocean Mission Initiatives, in particular in the Atlantic Basin and also in the European Sustainable Blue Economy Partnership.
Mr. Luis Lozano Gutiérrez	Mr. Luis Lozano Gutiérrez is the Executive Director at EuroMarine, specializing in fostering collaboration with and within marine sciences across Europe. Prior to this, Luis was an independent consultant leading a SME specialized in Blue Economy projects. He also serves as an expert evaluator and rapporteur for the European Commission, contributing to the assessment and development of EU research and innovation projects.
Dr. Ingrid Puillat,	Dr. Ingrid Puillat is a marine researcher with expertise in marine observation and scientific management and design of research infrastructures. She was the scientific coordinator of three successive EU research infrastructure projects at EU-level: JERICO-FP7, JERICO-NEXT, JERICO-S3 and the former coordinator of JERICO-DS. Currently, she serves as the Director General of the European Multidisciplinary Seafloor and water column Observatory (EMSO-ERIC), leading advancements in European marine science of the deep ocean.
Mr. Ian Gauci Borda	Mr. Ian Gauci Borda is the Executive National Contact Point (NCP) for Health, the Cancer Mission, Widening, the European Research Area, and Research Infrastructures. He specializes in supporting researchers and organizations in accessing EU funding opportunities and fostering collaboration. His work focuses on advancing research and innovation within strategic EU programs and initiatives. He also has a long experience in HE funded projects & particularly on how to implement synergies at regional & country level.
Dr. Mathieu Doussineau	Mathieu Doussineau is a policy analyst and researcher currently working for the European Future Innovation System (EFIS) Centre. His work focuses on governance mechanisms, policy evaluation, and the use of data for governance and evidence-based policy. Mathieu worked at the European Commission's Joint Research Centre (JRC) in Seville, where he was involved in the implementation of smart specialisation strategies (S3) and the development of synergies between funding across EU regions. Mathieu's research interests include data and innovation ecosystems, Artificial Intelligence for innovation policy governance and the impact of research and innovation policies on societal challenges. He co-authored key EC reports, including "Exploring synergies between EU Cohesion policy and Horizon 2020 funding across European Regions" and "Smart Specialization and Blue Biotechnology in Europe". Mathieu is an engineer by training and holds a PhD in applied economics.

g. REMORA’s PERT

REMORA’s activities are implemented through 6 workpackages as described in the following PERT.

Figure 8: REMORA’s PERT diagramme

h. Main project results

Project results are tangible outputs and materials intended to reach specific audiences, ensuring their accessibility and relevance. REMORA’s main results are presented in Figure 2.

Figure 9 - REMORA’s main expected results

i. Summarized expected Outcomes and Impacts

To ensure of the relevance of CDE activities, the plan used the expected changes and benefits arising from the appropriate use of results by the identified target groups as guiding information. Table 5 summarizes the main expected outcomes and impacts as described in REMORA’s grant agreement.

Figure 10: REMORA’s main expected outcomes and impacts

At organizational level	At the 3 regions level	At European level
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Improved Human Resources strategy and capacities ▪ Increased competitiveness and reputation in applications for European and international research funding ▪ Synergies included in ESIF funding ▪ Higher participation success in Horizon Europe and more consortium leadership roles ▪ Increased cooperation within the 3 partners ▪ Staff members empowered to promote their assets at EU level and collaborate` 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Overcoming locked-in effects for former mono-beneficiaries funded under ERDF ▪ Better use of R&I infrastructure funded under ERDF ▪ Regional smart specialization strategies promoting synergies between ESIF and HorizonEU ▪ Mobilisation of national and EU resources for strategic investments 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Improved visibility of OR R&I systems ▪ Strengthened competitiveness of R&I actors in Widening countries ▪ Reformed R&I systems and institutions leading to increased attractiveness and retention of research talents ▪ Increased science and innovation capacity for regional systems in the 3 regions

ANNEX 3 : REMORA events in details

WP events	Description
WP1 (Organizations strategy and individual capacities):	
- Study visit at DTU	A visit to discover DTU research facilities and institutional practices
- 1 st and 2 nd series of internal workshops	Workshop within CITEB, OOM, OKEANOS to analyze their strengths and weaknesses regarding the 4 dimensions of Excellence for ERA : Human resources, Responsible Research and Innovation, Funding synergies, Horizon Europe strategy
- online mutual learning event 1 and 2	Events to share perspectives on the 4 dimensions between the 3 centers
- WP1 trainings	Training to build capacity on the 4 dimensions
WP2 (Joint internalisation strategy):	
- WP2 Joint workshop for R&I assets 1 & 2	Workshops gathering CITEB, OOM and OKEANOS and marine experts to help them identify R&I niches with EU added Value on which the 3 centers should cooperate
- WP2 Joint workshop for EU intelligence 3, 4, 5, 6	Workshops to increase the 3 centers staffs on the main networks, calls, and policies in the Marine R&I sector
- Joint internationalization strategy webinar	Webinar to define/refine the joint internationalization strategy
WP3 (Networking activities):	
- Symposium at La Reunion (M16)	A scientific symposium in La Reunion to define new project collaborations between partners and with also high level experts
- WP3 Joint webinars 1, 2, 3	Webinars to promotion the Joint internationalization strategy towards EU champions and networks
- Symposium at Madeira (M21)	A scientific symposium in Madeira to define new project collaborations between partners and with also high level experts
- WP3 Horizon Europe Incubator hackathons	Online meetings to build proposals
- WP3 networking preparatory meetings	Meeting to help researchers maximize the impacts of their networking activities
WP4 (Systematization and replicability):	
- Policy workshops 1, 2, 3, 4	Workshops gathering policymakers from the 3 regions and experts at EU level to help develop new ERDF tools to support funding synergies with Horizon Europe and avoid the substitution effect
- Regional workshops (one in La Reunion and one in Madeira)	Workshop to disseminate REMORA's tools towards other Regional R&I organizations and help exploit them to mimic REMORA's pathways
WP5 (Communication & Dissemination):	
- Communication team Workshops (M3 → M6)	Workshops gathering the communication team in order to prepare the CDE plan
- Dissemination webinar for OR R&I policymakers (M31)	A webinar targeting policy makers from other Outermost regions to disseminate REMORA's policy tools
- Dissemination webinar for Widening R&I organizations (M32)	A webinar targeting Widening R&I organizations to disseminate REMORA's institutional tools
- Dissemination event (M33)	A workshop targeting European policymakers to disseminate REMORA's policy tools
WP6 (Management & coordination)	
- KOM, Project Meeting (PM) 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8	Kick off meeting and project meetings
- REMORA general assembly during Project Meeting 3, 6, 8	The General assembly will gather REMORA's team and other staff members not directly involved in REMORA
- REMORA final conference	Project final conference will be held in brussels

ANNEX 4 : Summary of potentiel events and journals for dissemination of REMORA results

Center	Key scientific events during REMORA lifetime	Key Scientific journals for Ocean research
OOM	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - SciComPT 2025 : April 9 to 11 on Madeira Island. - APOcean 2025 : The Portuguese Oceanography Society - Copernicus Marine 2025 / One Ocean science: Nice, France 4–6 June 2025 - EGU 2025: European geoscience Union ; 27 April–2 May 2025, in Vienna and online - Ocean Sciences Meeting 2026: 22-27 Feb 2026 in Glasgow 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Frontiers in Marine Science, Scientific Reports, Journal of Physical Oceanography, JGR
CITEB	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - https://biotechnologycongress.com/europe/ https://www.eubce.com/ ; - 11th International Fisheries Observer and Monitoring Conference (https://ifomc.org/) - Cephalopod International Advisory Council 2025 (https://cephalopod.wordpress.com/) - 7th International Conference on Fish Telemetry (Etats-Unis) - Working Parties de Commission de Thons de l'océan Indien (CTOI) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - No possibility for Open access journals (difficulties to produce the paper in the frametime of the project as an eligible expense) - Marine Biology, Marine & Freshwater Research, Journal of the Marine Biological Association of the United Kingdom, Aquatic Living Resources, Zoosystema, Fishery Bulletin, Fisheries Science. - Targets : Zootaxa, Deep Sea Research, Cybium, etc... »
OKEANOS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 2024 AAORIA All-Atlantic Ocean Research and Innovation Alliance, - Ocean Literacy : EMSEA Annual Conference, SciComPT - Deep-Sea Biology Symposium, Ocean Sciences Meeting, International Ocean Colour Science Meeting, Annual European Cetacean Society Conference, 25th Biennial Conference on the Biology of Marine Mammals, International Symposium on Chemosynthesis-Based Ecosystems, International Conference MICRO, International Marine Debris Conference, International Sea Turtle Symposium, World Fisheries Congress, (ICES/PICES/FAO) Small Pelagic Fish: Key Resources for Social and Ecological Systems, International Symposium Deep-Sea Corals, Sharks International 2026 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Frontiers in Marine Science, acta ethologica, - Marine policy